

Deliverable: Mapping of knowledge gaps and recommendations for new data generation and method development

Workpackage 1

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SUMMARY OF RESULTS FROM EJP DISCOVER

WORK PACKAGE 1:

RAPID REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND KNOWLEDGE MAPPING FOR SOURCE ATTRIBUTION

Introduction

This is a brief summary of the efforts to map knowledge gaps in the field of source attribution related to the following group of organisms: *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC/STEC and antimicrobial resistant (AMR) bacteria with a focus on ESBL/AmpC *E. coli*.

The knowledge mapping is based on a literature review which, due to time constraints has been realized as a rapid review which means that it still is a systematic review but with limited comprehensiveness.

Literature search strategy

We used Boolean keyword phrases in two data bases for scientific publications (Scopus and Web of Science) looking for works of the last 30 years (from 1990 to 2020). The keyword phrases looked for matches in titles, abstracts and keywords of the published literature. Separate searches were performed for each class of microorganism (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC, AMR).

Titles and Abstracts of the findings were reviewed and checked if the publications fulfilled the following inclusion criteria:

- 1) Only journal articles and reviews were considered
- 2) Only publications in English were considered
- 3) Only publications that report about performed/evaluated/reviewed/meta-analysed source attributions were considered or that report on data (e.g. analysis of outbreak data) which might be useful for source attribution
- 4) The source attribution is concerned with the zoonotic pathogens in question
- 5) The source attribution is concerned with climate zones that correspond to those of the EU (this excludes South America, Africa and parts of Asia)
- 6) Source attribution is concerned with commonly exposure paths of European citizens (e.g. source tracking of Laboratory-Acquired infections were excluded)

Publications which fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included in the corpus. The number of publications found for each group of organism is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of number of publications identified in the review for each category of microorganisms.

Organism	Publications identified
<i>Salmonella</i>	133
<i>Campylobacter</i>	68
VTEC	41
AMR	13
Σ	255

Tagging publications using categories

Tagging happened in the program EndNote using the custom fields to define the categories like "Source", "Method", "Organism" or "Location" of the source attribution study.

Each of the just mentioned categories has a number of fixed possible values, which were attributed to each publication after reviewing the main text of the publication. Examples for the values of the categories are for the category “Source”: production animal-cattle, production animal-chicken, companion animal-bird, companion animal-cat, companion animal-dog, wild animal-rabbit, meat, meat-beef, meat-chicken, etc. Examples for the values of the category “Method” are: antibiotyping, case-control study, interview, MLST, outbreak data, phage typing, etc.

Knowledge mapping

The tagged publication data was exported from EndNote to a file in the bibtex format. This bibtex file was subsequently read into the statistical software R for further analysis. In R we created two dimensional visualizations of the numbers of publications related to source-method combinations was produced. We did these visualizations by organism (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of a knowledge map for *Salmonella*.

The darker the hue in a cell the more publications there are for the corresponding source-method combination in the corpus of identified literature. The red number in a cell says how many publications have been identified. The empty white cells are, following the style of 19th century geographical maps, the white spots of our knowledge map, indicating a lack of knowledge about that area. Of course what we have here is not exactly a knowledge-map but a publication-map. However, taking scientific publication as a surrogate of scientific knowledge our map is a surrogate of a knowledge map. The white spots on this map thus resemble (in this surrogative sense) knowledge gaps.

Summary of results and recommendations

The broad trends found from the analysis of knowledge maps for the various microorganisms are summarized in Table 2.

order to calculate the comparative weight of evidence. It might well be that the published literature harbors only a limited amount of such publications.

Table 2. Broad summary of the results obtained from the various knowledge maps created for the four kinds of organism.

Organism	Gaps in knowledge related to sources and methods	
	In food/livestock source	In non-food source
Salmonella	<p>Flour throughout all methods</p> <p>Risk assessment, systematic reviews, time series analysis and meta-analysis throughout all sources</p>	<p>Wild animals (deer, birds, rabbit), water environment especially with respect to risk/exposure assessment</p> <p>Risk assessment, systematic reviews, time series analysis and meta-analysis throughout all sources</p>
Campylobacter	<p>Flour throughout all methods</p> <p>Systematic reviews, time series analysis, case-case studies and meta-analysis throughout all sources</p>	<p>Human throughout all methods</p> <p>companion animals (more horses, birds, rabbits, rodents, peeting zoos and reptiles less cats and dogs) and wild animals particularly with respect to time series analysis, risk assessment methods</p> <p>risk assessment, time series, systematic review, meta-analysis, and case-case-studies throughout all sources</p>
VTEC/STEC	<p>Flour, grains, nuts throughout all methods</p> <p>risk/exposure assessment, meta-analysis, the use of surveillance data, case-case- studies and systematic reviews throughout all sources</p>	<p>Human, travel, wild animal throughout all methods</p> <p>risk/exposure assessment, meta-analysis, surveillance data, case-case- studies and systematic reviews throughout all sources</p>
AMR	Not applicable (too little data)	Not applicable (to little data)

Based on the results of WP 1 we arrive at the following general recommendations for new studies and/or methods that are needed to fill existent knowledge gaps:

- Include flour as possible source in source attribution studies throughout all organisms
- Advance risk assessment studies as source attribution approach throughout all organisms

- Explore/evaluate time series analysis as one potential new methodological approach for source attribution
- Advance source attribution studies for *Salmonella* including/with a focus on wild animals and water environments as possible sources
- Advance source attribution studies for *Campylobacter* including/with a focus on wild animals, companion animals and infected humans as possible sources
- Advance source attribution studies for VTEC/STEC including/with a focus on wild animals, travel and infected humans as possible sources
- Advance source attribution studies for AMR organisms throughout all organisms